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List of Acronyms

APECS Association of Polar Early Career Scientists

ASM Arctic Science Ministerial

EC European Commission

EPB European Polar Board

ESA European Space Agency

DoA Description of Action

MST Management Support Team

PAB Policy Advisory Board

R&I Research & Innovation

ToR Term of Reference

UN. United Nation

WP Work Package

Executive Summary

This Deliverable presents a first synthesis on the performed policy advice activities carried out by the EU-PolarNet 2 project within WP5 (“Policy Advice, Dissemination and Communication”). The first section describes the status of the Policy Advisory Board (PAB), including roles, responsibilities, the first meeting and the nomination of the chair and co-chairs. The second section provides a summary of the events organised by the project which can be identified as policy advice actions.

Introduction

This Deliverable presents a first summary of the policy-advice-oriented activities carried out by the EU-PolarNet 2 project from the beginning of the project up to June 2022.

This report is part of WP5 (“Policy Advice, Dissemination and Communication”) activities and falls within Task 5.1 actions (see DoA under WP5 description of work), focusing on:

- 1) Implementing a Policy Advisory Board (PAB) to give policy advice on request at national or EU levels and building durable capacity for adequate policy responses from the European Polar research community.
- 2) Giving explicit and politically implementable policy recommendations on requests.
- 3) Pro-actively translating the outcome of the research prioritisation process, from WP3 activities, into policy briefings for political actors, research funders, researchers and other stake- and right-holders. Policy briefings and a Town Hall meeting will be coordinated with related actions from the EU Polar Cluster projects.

This deliverable presents in one section the status of the PAB, including a summary of the first PAB meeting (7th June 2021) and the appointment of a chair-and co-chair. A second section provides a summary of the events organised by the EU-PolarNet 2 project, which can be identified as policy advice actions.

Status of the Policy Advisory Board (PAB)

The Policy Advisory Board (PAB) has been established by the EU-PolarNet 2 project with the aim to provide an evidence-based policy advice to the EC and other decision makers. It includes members nominated by the EU-PolarNet 2 partners who represent the contact points for advice based on national expertise. The PAB will closely cooperate with the EU Polar Cluster and the Policy Advisory Group of the EPB.

The Terms of Reference (ToR) of the Policy Advisory Board, including scope and roles-nomination-organisation is presented in the relative Deliverable D5.3 (“Implementation of a PAB incl. terms of reference, mandate and scope of the board”) submitted in May 2021. It can be downloaded here: <https://eu-polarnet.eu/docs/d5-3-implementation-of-a-pab-incl-terms-of-reference-mandate-and-scope-of-the-board/>.

The first PAB meeting has been held on 7th June 2021. It aimed to introduce the PAB members and the EU-PolarNet 2 partners dealing with policy advice to each other and to show how the policy advice will work in EU-PolarNet 2. Additionally, the procedure to select the chair for the PAB was discussed.

During the meeting, the following PAB tasks were presented, as extracted by the meeting minutes:

1. To seek input from national experts and provide fast responses as required to the EC and national decision makers to address any urgent needs and demands for scientific advice. Usually, requests by the EC are transferred to the PAB through the EU-PolarNet 2 MST. The MST is retrieving the responses from the PAB and forwards a compilation to the EC, as well as to the whole PAB.
2. To support EU-PolarNet 2 in transferring scientific knowledge to regional, national and EU-level policymakers by actively preparing thematic policy briefings e.g., through meetings in Brussels or fact sheets to contribute to evidence-based decision making. EU-PolarNet 2 plans two policy briefings and one larger Town Hall event in Brussels.
3. To recommend themes and experts for the active policy briefings and fact sheets.

The following PAB chair and co-chair have been respectively appointed: Dr. Volker Rachold - Head of the German Arctic Office at the Alfred Wegener Institute - and Dr. Sonia Ramos Garcia – Technical Secretariat of the Spanish Polar Committee (status: July 2021).

This deliverable is focusing on the pro-active policy advice conducted by EU-PolarNet 2 until June 2022 towards stakeholders, researchers, politicians and the interested public through the events reported below.

Summary of the policy-advice oriented events

This section reports a summary of the events – reported in chronological order from least to most recent - organised by the EU-PolarNet 2 project as policy-advice-oriented activities. These events are part of the list of the Dissemination activities described in Deliverable D5.4 (“First progress report on dissemination activities”) submitted in October 2021 -see <https://eu-polarnet.eu/docs/d5-4-first-progress-report-on-dissemination-activities/> and part of the list of webinars presented in Deliverable D1.5 (“1st Summary and recording of thematic webinars dedicated to improving European cooperation”) - see <https://eu-polarnet.eu/docs/d1-5-1st-summary-and-recording-of-thematic-webinars-dedicated-to-improving-european-cooperation/>.

Name of the event	Visit of Finland’s Arctic and Antarctic Ambassador Petteri Vuorimäki and his team
Date	06/10/2020
Place	University of Oulu, Finland
Organiser	EU-PolarNet 2, Ministry of Foreign Affairs Finland, University of Oulu
Link of the event (if any)	Not available
Target audience	Policy makers, as well as University leaders and Arctic researchers
Policy advice objective	Intent to share information about EU-PolarNet 2 to Finnish Arctic and Antarctic Ambassador and discuss on European polar research and linkages to other relevant Polar policies and research.

Name of the event	EU Polar Science Week – EU-PolarNet 2 Kick-Off meeting, public session & EU Polar Cluster – ESA day
Date	26 – 27/10/2020
Place	Online meeting
Organiser	EU-PolarNet 2 project
Link of the event (if any)	https://eo4polar.esa.int/#background
Target audience	Politicians as well as scientists
Policy advice objective	<p>Intent to bring together the European Polar science community and reinforce European cooperation for Polar Science. The EU-PolarNet2 kick-off meeting has been organised during the EU Polar Science Week with the intent to have a greater impact and visibility within the European Polar Science Community.</p> <p>More specifically, the Polar Science Week aimed to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying major Polar scientific challenges, observation gaps and research needs for the coming years. • Define major scientific priorities in polar research that may drive EC and ESA collaborative activities in the coming years and formulate recommendations for an EC-ESA Common Polar Science Agenda. • Share latest results in polar science with a focus on Earth Observation, and promote networking and collaborative research in Polar sciences, bringing together different expertise, data and resources in a systemic manner, as stated during the ESA-EU Polar Cluster day on 27/10/2020

Name of the event	All-Atlantic Ocean Research Forum
Date	03-04/12/2020
Place	Online congress
Organiser	EU-PolarNet 2 project
Link of the event (if any)	https://allatlanticocean.org/view/events/all-atlantic-ocean-research-forum
Target audience	Policy makers, civil society representatives, entrepreneurs
Policy advice objective	Intent to explain the importance of the poles in the Atlantic Ocean context.

Name of the event	All-Atlantic 2021 side event - Networking from pole to pole: facilitating access for research and infrastructure - Ministerial High-Level & Stakeholder Conference
Date	02/06/2021
Place	Online webinar organised as a side event of the All-Atlantic 2021 conference held in Azores, Portugal
Organiser	EU-PolarNet 2 project and the European Polar Board (EPB)
Link of the event (if any)	The recorded presentations are available online in the EU-PolarNet Youtube Channel through the link https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=z_DdQAGqztQ .
Target audience	Policy makers, civil society representatives, entrepreneurs
Policy advice objective	The aim was to discuss on how to develop a network facilitating access for the All-Atlantic partners to national research facilities and infrastructures at the poles. The event aimed also at identifying challenges, best practices, and next steps for implementing cross border access to polar research facilities and infrastructure (see D1.5 for more details on the presentations and relative speakers).

Name of the event	European Perspectives on the Arctic Science Ministerial Process
Date	28/04/2021
Place	Online webinar
Organiser	EU-PolarNet 2 project and the European Polar Board (EPB)
Link of the event (if any)	The recorded presentations were made available online on the European Polar Board YouTube Channel through the link https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p4_f4uHBK2A .
Target audience	European entities working to coordinate different aspects of Arctic science and research and policy, including the Icelandic Ministry of Foreign Affairs and European Commission representative
Policy advice objective	Aim to explore a European perspective on the Arctic Science Ministerial (ASM) process, including underlining developments since ASM2 and contributions to ASM3. The webinar aimed to explore how existing structures and entities for coordination of polar research in Europe help to facilitate the activities working towards the aims of ASM, nurturing a strong and cohesive European community for Arctic research. Invited speakers discussed how different programmes align with ASM objectives in the context of the four ASM3 Themes: Observe, Understand, Respond, and Strengthen along a session with different presentations.

Name of the event	COP26 Side event: “Polar warming, global warning”
Date	03/11/2021
Place	Online webinar organised as a side event of the UN Climate Change Conference COP26 held in Glasgow, United Kingdom
Organiser	EU Polar Cluster
Link of the event (if any)	The recording is available online on EU Climate Action YouTube Channel at the link https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5JKaoyilSHM .
Target audience	Scientific community and general public
Policy advice objective	The “Polar warming, global warning” webinar included several presentations by world-leading Arctic and Antarctic climate scientists - from the Cluster projects and European research institutions. These presentations were framed in the context of the new EU Arctic Policy, the Antarctic Treaty and COP26 and had the purpose of showing that Polar Regions are experiencing faster changes than most of the regions in the world.

Name of the event	“The new EU Arctic Policy and Research and Innovation”
Date	24/11/2021
Place	Online webinar
Organiser	EU Polar Cluster, EU-PolarNet 2 and the European Polar Board (EPB)
Link of the event (if any)	The registration is available online in the European Polar Board YouTube channel at the link https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2W1V6cUDo00 .
Target audience	Scientific community, representatives of the European Commission and members of the EU Polar Cluster projects
Policy advice objective	Aim to provide a comprehensive overview on the webinar issue and especially on linking Policy to Science and its stakeholders. The presentations were organised in two topics: Arctic Policy and Arctic-related EU Polar Cluster projects.

Name of the event	“Who owns the Arctic? – An introduction to Arctic Governance”
Date	09/06/2022
Place	Online webinar
Organiser	EU-PolarNet 2 project and APECS (Association of Polar Early Career Scientists)
Link of the event (if any)	The registration is available online in the EU-PolarNet2 YouTube channel at the link https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jGPo6d8zEJk .
Target audience	Scientific community, representatives of the European Commission and members of the EU Polar Cluster projects
Policy advice objective	Aim to present the Arctic governance aspects. Due to the increasing interest and awareness of the global significance of the Arctic, questions about stewardship and governance of the region are indeed being asked more frequently. Governance structures suitable for effectively addressing the challenges and opportunities facing the circumpolar North are becoming more relevant than ever. This webinar gives an overview of the legal regime of the Arctic and outlines the existing Arctic governance structures.

Conclusions

This deliverable includes the list of the events held so far by the project and that can be identified as the project policy-advice actions.

Beside these events, a webinar with focus on the Antarctic Treaty and one on Permafrost research in the context of the new EU Arctic Policy are foreseen for autumn 2022.

Up to now, EU-PolarNet 2 received no requests for evidence-based policy advice from decision makers or the EC.